

1. Introduction

Tanzania is among the African countries praised to have maintained its peace since attaining of her Independence in 1961 (Hofmeier, 1997). However, different conflicts have been occurring and recently the land conflict. The most documented cause and reason for land conflicts in Tanzania has been increase or growth of population for both human beings and other living organisms such as animals while land remains the same, so as human being strive in life to get their basic needs they need land as a crucial resource to cultivate, hunt, and pasturing. (Wehrmann, 2008). The persistence and ongoing conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in Tanzania have not been a new problem instead it can be traced as far as before and after colonialism. The 1990s onwards land conflict in Tanzania has led to loss of lives, destruction of property, and creation of virtual war zones (Seddon and Sumberg, 1997). Henceforth, this paper has examined the persistence of land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in Tanzania.

1.1 Problem Statement

There are numerous research papers on land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in Tanzania but still three main problems increase decade after decade. One, the cause of the land conflict in Tanzania lays on land demarcation where there is no clear land boundary for the villages of pastoralists and villages for farmers. However much the land reform policy states the demarcation but it's not yet to be clearly imposed henceforth continuous land conflict is noticed in Tanzania. (Msuya, 2009). Two, the cause of land conflict in Tanzania is due to the movement of pastoralists from one place to another which is their nature. The conflict henceforth arises when pastoralists move toward the farmers land and let their animals feed on the crops. (Mwamfupe, 2015). Three, in contrast some research scholars suggest that pastoralists require large land areas as they keep large livestock but since they lose their land an example drawn from the Maasai residing in the northern part of Tanzania, the government takes away the land as part of the national reserve, henceforth creating a new group of the agro-pastoralists resulting in conflict particularly over land resource. (Kajembe et al. 2003). Late research scholars points out that these conflicts are now being witnessed in predominantly crop cultivating areas which had no prior experience of livestock keeping. For this reason farming communities label the pastoralists as "invaders". (Mwambashi, 2015). Integrating with Tanzania land policy reform which includes the Land Act and Village Land Act of 1999 as amended in 2004 to develop other land tenure arrangements. The reason for the reforms lies in attempts to make land in a free market system and make it accessible to foreign investment. While the purpose is made clear on the resolving of the conflict these policies have led to conflicts between the farmers and pastoralists, as they are not based on social realities. This paper indicates that the reason for the magnitude increase of land conflict in recent decade, between the farmers and pastoralists' in Tanzania in most two sub-regional regions the Northern and Central part respectively is due to the approach used to resolve land conflict in Tanzania which is top-bottom approach. The use of excessive force is not only unsustainable but also deepens hatred between the two parties; the farmers and pastoralists. (Japhet, 2021).

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this paper were threefold: **first**, is to analyze why there is persistence of land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in the Northern and Central sub-regional parts of Tanzania. **Second**, is to study the land policy reform and how applicable on resolving the land conflict between

the farmers-pastoralist in Tanzania. **And third**, is to suggest the way forward to curb with the withering problem of farmers and pastoralists land conflict in Tanzania.

1.3 Research Questions

This paper intends to answer the following threefold questions: **First**, why land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in Northern and Central sub-regional parts of Tanzania is persistent? **Second**, to what extent is the land policy reform applicable to resolving the land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in Tanzania? **And third**, what are the suggestions to curb with the withering problem of farmers and pastoralists land conflict in Tanzania?

1.4 Rationale of the Study

The researcher has explored the problem of this study which is land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists that has been going on in Tanzania for so long without an end regardless the government and non-governmental efforts in resolving the problem. And for this reason the researcher has incorporated the field of peace studies and conflict analysis theory (Galtung, 1969) to suggest a way forward on how to curb with the withering problem of persistence land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in Tanzania.

1.5 Importance of the Study

Due to the persistence of land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in Tanzania which has been and still is a problem, the researcher ought to put effort by studying what has been missing in other research scholar's work and what has not been done to solve the ongoing problem. It is of these reasons that the researcher thought it is of importance to devote time and study on the re-occurring problem and henceforth contribute in the field of peace studies by suggesting the best practice and policy to be carried out so as to help in resolving the land conflict problem in Tanzania, this along with other best solutions given by other research scholars, non- government organizations, as well as the government in their previous published documents which the researcher appreciates their efforts.

2. Literature review

2.1 Survey of related literature

This section provides a literature review of the land conflict in Tanzania. As Lederach (1997: 94) argues, 'the greatest resource for sustaining peace in the long term is always rooted in the local people and their culture'. Tanzanian authorities are finding it increasingly difficult to deal with persistent conflict between the farmers and pastoralists as the northern and the central regional part respectively violent and sometimes deadly clashes have been raging for decades as farmers and pastoralists fight over land (Makoye, 2014). Statistics show that Tanzania worst conflict between pastoralists and farmers

occurred in December 2000 in Kilosa District, Morogoro Region, where 38 farmers were killed. Hostilities again reignited in 2008 and eight people were killed, several houses set on fire and livestock stolen. (Benjaminsen et al, 2009). Corruption has been associated with the ongoing land conflict especially in the northern regional part where Maasai pastoralists allegedly invaded villages in the disputed forest reserve and set homes on fire. Local farmers accused district officials of colluding with Maasai pastoralists to intimidate farmers living on the reserve in an attempt to chase them off their land. (Mesiaya, 2014). While Meshack Saidimu, a Maasai pastoralist said that most of the conflicts occurred because the government has not set aside areas for pastoralists. He said: "I think we are being

made scapegoats for all these problems”. The Maasai are disciplined people and they don’t just hurt somebody for the sake of it (Saidimu, 2014). The farmers complain that pastoralists let their animals destroy on their crops by letting the livestock enter the farms while searching for water and pasture (Myenzi, 2004).

From the literature review, the researcher’s view is that there should be critical consideration to pastoralists since they are the category who are most affected by being shifted from their origin land to the other with number of facts but with reported earlier research it seems the relocated area doesn’t suit their cultural lifestyle having large number of life stock it needs enough space and where there is access of water. Therefore the researcher feels there is a need for the Government of Tanzania to give equal attention from the ground to both pastoralists and farmers and engage them in conflict resolution by suggesting suitable and accomplishable solutions. (Japhet, 2021)

2.2 Conceptual Framework

In this section, the researcher has defined seven terms used throughout this paper. The first term is **land conflict** as defined by a sociologist is a social fact in which at least two parties or groups are involved and whose origins are different in interests regarding a given piece of land – possibly aggravated by differences in the social position of the parties. (Imbusch, 1999). Operationally, it refers to the land conflict between the pastoralists and the farmers in Tanzania. Second, is a **farmer** a person engaged or works under the umbrella of agriculture, a person who cultivates land or grow crops for human consumption. (Merriam- Webster Dictionary, 1828). The third term is a **pastoralist** a person concerned with raising of livestock in large quantity. It is animal husbandry: such as goats, cattle, and sheep. (Oxford Dictionary, 1989). To proceed further this paper has incorporated the term **land policy reform** in Tanzania land policy reform of 1999 consists of two acts; the Village Land Act which governs land in village areas and the Land Act which governs land in cities. The reform aims at setting up a new land administration structure at the local level by vesting power over land in the villages. (URT, 1999). **Tanzania** is the case study used for this paper therefore the researcher defines as a country situated in Eastern part of Africa with a total of thirty one regions both in the mainland being twenty six and Island Zanzibar being five. The country has five sub-regions which are the Northern, Southern, Eastern, Western and Central part of Tanzania. (Japhet, 2021). **Since this is a cultural paper**, the researcher also identifies the two conflicting groups who are the farmers and pastoralists as an example in this research paper who have different cultural type with different cultural practice. For example the Maasai are the pastoralist whose culture is totally different from the Sukuma who are the farmers. **Culture** refers to the beliefs, customs, values and activities of a particular group of people at a particular time. (Antonia, 2019). In this paper, it refers to the cultures of the farmers and the pastoralists in Tanzania. The last term is **peace building** is an structural mechanism involves a wide range of efforts by diverse actors in government and civil society at the community, national, and international levels to address the immediate impacts and root causes of conflict before, during, and after violent conflict occurs. (Khan, 2020)

2.3 Theoretical Framework

The researcher has incorporated Galtung’s (1969) theory of conflict violence triangle which includes **direct, structural and cultural violence**, respectively. This theory is relevant to this study and it will guide the whole study for main three main reasons; **first**, direct violence is prevalent in this research problem as it is coherent as an example of presence of physical violence which is indicated in the surveyed related literature. **Second**, structural violence which is also foreseen in this research presence of social structure mainly the farmers and pastoralists creating social injustice. **Third**, cultural

violence which is clearly seen throughout the research which is in between the two different cultural identities, the farmers and pastoralists respectively.

2.4 Contributions of the Study

The researcher has observed that the problem behind these clashes is deeper than what the society thinks as it has been persistent for so long despite having some earlier research done laying down suggestions on how to resolve the conflict between the two groups, but also the efforts done by the government and non-government by incorporating the top-bottom approach but still the problem has proven to grow. Therefore, the researcher aims to fill the gap by suggesting a **bottom-up approach**, which will involve all concerned parties who are the government officials, non-government organizations, the farmers and pastoralists whom are the target of these conflicts in the negotiation process, and there **must be a forum** where farmers and pastoralists openly talk about their problems. Not only imposing the laws from the top which might or might not be relevant and have biasness henceforth each party thinks one is favoured.

3. Methodology

This paper is an analytical type of research study. Because it has the available facts on the land policy reform in Tanzania but also the related information already available to analyze the problem of land conflict between farmers and pastoralist in Tanzania. This paper has used a qualitative technique approach to analyze the findings of study. The study design of the paper is a case study design because the research has only concentrate on one concentrated area which is Tanzania but also the consistency of two groups that have clash over the land. The source of data used is secondary source of data. While the tools of data used are published journals, articles, news and land policy reform of Tanzania. Importantly, the latest news and parliamentary discussions about the land conflict issue is monitored and reflected in this paper. Lastly, the concentrated area of study are mainly the Northern and Central Sub-Regional Parts of Tanzania, because among all five regional parts of Tanzania the above mentioned are highly affected by land conflict between pastoralists and farmers but also geographically pastoralists originally are from the Northern part while farmers cover the rest of the sub-regional parts.

4. Findings

4.1 Reasons for the Persistence of Land Conflict

As reported by AyoTV online news on April, 2021; the researcher finds out that non-involvement of government decision to pastoralists in regard to shifting of their origin area of settlement causes to land conflict. In the news Maasai the pastoralist's were asked to move as an immediate action from the area they are residing at Ngorongoro which the government terms it as national reserve. This decision is likely to lead to land conflict during the movement as animals need to be fed henceforth invasion of the farmer's land. **Second**, as reported by AyoTv online news on May, 2021; Hon Mashimba Ndaki from Ministry for Livestock and Fisheries said Tabora has high number of pastoralists but also inclusive in land conflict cases between farmers and pastoralist and this is due to land scarcity as large portion of land is set for national reserve henceforth the remaining land doesn't meet the needs for both farmers and pastoralists. **Third**, drought that is caused by unfavourably climate change, environmental degradation caused by increase of human activities has led to persistence fight over fertile land between the farmers and pastoralists in Tanzania.

4.2 Applicability of the Land Policy Reform

First, the researcher finds out that the land policy reform is weak as it doesn't clearly enhance the implementation of its set laws. For instance in the village act requires every village to have in place a land use plan, many villages are yet to implement this due to lack of supervision as the authorities responsible act irresponsible, but also corruption, and lack of evaluation in this department. **Second**, the researcher finds out that the land policies are odd and don't effectively meet the need of the recent problem henceforth it proves to be weak. **Third**, despite amendments and clear set laws the land policy proves to be best in document while it lacks practicability.

4.3 Suggestions to the Problem

The researcher suggests that to curb with the withering problem of farmers and pastoralists land conflict in Tanzania, **first**, there must be involvement from the grass root level to both cultural groups. **Second**, concerned Ministry, Department, Local Government should set up clear and defined land mark for both farmers and pastoralists to avoid invasion. **Third**, the respective office should enhance effective implementation over the set land policy. **Forth**, pastoralists in this case should adapt new pastoralism method which involves construction of dams (Mabwawa in Swahili) and growing of grass on their given land. This will help even in drought season they don't need to move from their land which mostly leads to invasion of farmers land and thereafter intensifying to land conflict.

5. Summary and Policy implication

5.1 Summary

Galtung's Theory of structural violence was applied to the land conflict in Tanzania; cultural violence to the conflict between the famers and pastoralists who have two different cultural identities and physical violence to the crossing the line between the land of two groups which caused physical altercations and police action. For example; land conflict in Kilosa District during 2000. The land reform law clearly was necessary but insufficient as peace-building effort of the government. The summary findings can be summarized in the figure 1 below;

Figure 1: Japhet's Model of Land Conflict and Land Reform Policy as Peace-building in Tanzania

5.2 Policy Implication

For the policy implication the researcher suggests that to end the ongoing and persistence land conflict between the farmers and pastoralists in Tanzania. The Tanzanian land policy should include the following measures; **first**, to enhance total inclusiveness this will avoid biasness and further complains form each cultural group the farmers and pastoralists respectively. **Second**, bottom-up approach should be adopted by the respective ministry. **Third**, time to time amendment of the land policy is required this will make the policy effective and able to tackle the recent problems. **Forth**, the researcher suggest that grounded practice is also an effective measure to be considered on overcoming the land conflict problem and last the concerned department should enhance there is effective policy implementation.

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